

NEW DESIGN APPROACHES FOR COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURES - REQUIREMENTS FOR ADVANCED MATERIALS, PROCESSES AND MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES

Christian Rueckert & Michael Kolax

*AIRBUS Deutschland GmbH
Huenefeldstr. 1-5
28199 Bremen
Germany*

ABSTRACT

In recent years, metal technologies were enhanced to an extent that, esp. for use in fuselage structures, already implies a certain end for future significant improvements. To ensure AIRBUS' position of technology leadership, coming along with cost effective design and manufacturing, a series of long-term projects was launched to develop a composite fuselage for future AIRBUS aircraft.

A broad use of advanced composites for primary and secondary structure, interior and equipment for the realization of such a revolutionary design should enable AIRBUS engineers to realize in a technological jump ahead cost reductions of 40% and weight reduction of 30% as well as maintenance reduction (no fatigue, no corrosion) and higher safety standards (30/40/++), compared to the actual aluminum baseline.

That means a very strong reduction of the direct operating costs (DOC), a very important number for the customer and his decision to buy an aircraft.

Several projects with national character have since evolved into a transnational project, bringing together under one roof all composite fuselage related activities of AIRBUS.

The paper gives an overview about the technological approach for composite applications in typical fuselage and the so far realized progress.

Keywords: composite fuselage, materials and processes, double skin design, weight and cost saving, advanced manufacturing

1. INTRODUCTION

The project focusing on typical fuselage targets at the development of a revolutionary design for tomorrow's fuselage structures. Fundamental for mission success is the elaboration of new design approaches, which are optimized for the use of composites from the very beginning.

A simple replacement of traditional metal fuselage design with an identical composite approach will not be sufficient to reach the project goals.

Parallel with first design studies for advanced composite fuselage structures, a broad approach was taken by AIRBUS engineers in close cooperation with university institutes and research facilities to develop new materials and according manufacturing technologies, thus creating an efficient network for composite fuselage research & development (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Example for Networking - Composite Fuselage Landscape Airbus Deutschland GmbH

2. OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH APPROACHES

To ensure all perspectives for 30% cost- and 40% weight reduction and other advantages like passenger comfort (humidity), a composite fuselage system will have to fulfill a variety of requirements.

Along with typical composite features like zero fatigue and corrosion, which already is a significant advantage compared to metal design, one project goal is to realize a structure with advanced safety standards.

In case of a post crash fire, the goal is to guarantee an evacuation period of 5 min. with full structure integrity. All FST (Fire-Smoke-Toxicity) requirements for interior and adjacent structural elements have to be fulfilled. In addition, still to be defined burn-thru requirements for outer structural components will have to be met.

Further on, the customer should be enabled to purchase a product that requires only little inspection for optimized economical service.

To ensure significant weight reduction, a maximum degree of function integration should be achieved. The project is aiming at the integration of cabin interior, system routings and special features like

- Impact shielding
- Thermal insulation
- Acoustical insulation

into primary structure. This can only be achieved with new design approaches.

It is obvious that the development of an optimized fuselage design, which targets from the very beginning at the realization of the project goals 30/40 (weight/cost reduction), is essential.

This process implies a parallel development of advanced composite materials, processes, manufacturing and testing technologies as well as enhanced calculation methods for an efficient structure-mechanical use.

3. NEW DESIGN APPROACHES FOR COMPOSITE FUSELAGE STRUCTURES

A simple conversion of a metal type of design is not in the position to achieve a breakthrough in weight- and cost saving. At maximum level, slight weight savings at neutral cost level seem realistic. Nevertheless, ongoing efforts within AIRBUS (TANGO) contribute a lot to create a solid knowledge basis in terms of gaining experience in

- Manufacturing and process handling of textiles and infusion
- Design and manufacturing of larger thermoplastic elements
- Combining a variety of different philosophies within one barrel

Also structural testing of TANGO barrels creates valuable data for next step R&D:

- Structural respond under load with chosen design
- Comparison between calculation and structural behavior in reality

In a multi-disciplinary study, double skin concepts were preferred compared to monolithic type of design in terms of possible potentials for weight and cost reduction (30/40) in AIRBUS typical fuselage. Figure 2 shows a typical example for a double skin design.

Figure 2: Example for Double Skin Design (Center Skin Concept)

The separation of load paths by attaching stiffening elements (frames, stringers) on opposite sides of a primary load bearing skin implies a potential weight reduction of up to 15% compared to monolithic metal design, just by eliminating intersections. An add-on impact shield would have to be attached, in this case in form of a core element with an outer covering layer (aerodynamic surface, impact detection). To keep add-on weight at low level, the double skin build-up should integrate functions from secondary structure, equipment or interior like thermal and acoustical insulation, fire protection (burn-thru) and moisture management.

Based on this preliminary design decision, according material and processes development is supported and performed.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF ADVANCED MATERIALS

Main driver for material development is the need to realize cost-effective lightweight structures, along with fulfilling all special requirements related with fuselage systems.

Apparently, advanced M&P/Manufacturing Technology cannot do the job alone, but contribute with all immanent properties to realize the technological jump ahead (see figure 3).

Figure 3: Contribution of Materials & Processes / Manufacturing Technology

Focus of work lies on

- Enhancement of mech. and phys. properties
- Improved damage tolerance (impact, open hole)
- Improved media resistance
- Fulfillment of all FST and burn-thru requirements
- Reduction of material costs
- Optimization of processing

In close cooperation with the research landscape, efforts are being undertaken to create new materials in every major field like

1. Resin systems
2. Textiles and textile processes
3. Infusion technologies
4. Thermoplastic materials and –processes
5. Bonding materials and –processes
6. Core materials

The initial phase of work was dedicated to “free thinking”, but with the design freeze for the realization of first test articles, an according selection of materials and processes has been made. In parallel, a steady output for AIRBUS production of ongoing programs had to be guaranteed.

4.1 RESIN SYSTEMS

Today’s standard thermoset resin systems like 6376 or 977-2 show no completely satisfying performance for a broad use in CFRP fuselage structures.

Together with research institutes some efforts are undertaken to improve resin properties in terms of

- FST and fire resistance
- Processing (low temperature, low pressure)
- Alternative curing (e.g. electron beam)
- Interaction with advanced textiles (e.g. NCF)

Examples are lo-temp curing resins for infusion technologies, dubbed catalytic resin systems, and fire retardant systems, dubbed combination resins.

For weight optimized manufacturing, the development of new prepreg resin systems is mandatory. According contacts with the composite industry are already initiated and start to pay off.

Although thermoset resin systems and related prepreg products are not yet optimized for fuselage applications, those materials nevertheless represent the mainstay for test article manufacturing.

4.2 TEXTILES AND TEXTILE PROCESSES

Research work is done on a variety of textile technologies, among which

- Braiding
- NCF
- Multiaxial knitting
- Tailored fiber placement (TFP)
- One-side stitching

are the most important. Textiles are highly flexible and can be purchased on a low cost basis. Additional stitching in z-direction aims in the case of stitching as preforming technology at the realization of integrated 3-D structures, or, in the case of reinforcement of 2-D lay-ups, at achieving higher design strain levels (weight reduction).

Taking into account the design pre-decision for double skin concepts with thickness of ca. 2 mm for the primary load bearing skin and ca. 1 mm for secondary outer skin, a broad use of textiles for large, plane structures does not allow weight optimized design.

For the time being, standard UD-tape ($s = 0.125 \text{ mm}$) enables optimum design at lowest weight. To meet the project's ambitious goals, a use of UD material for the realization of skins should be favored.

Further significant deficits of textiles are:

- Lacking philosophy for quality insurance, incoming inspection
- Poor reproducibility of textile mechanics
- Highly dependent on required infusion technology (e.g. RFI, RTM, VAP)

Textiles will be used where they promise to bring the biggest benefit. Typical applications, which will be verified with demo components and test articles, are e.g. frames, fittings or local reinforcement of cutouts like for windows and doors (see figure 4).

Figure 4 – Examples for Textile Applications (left – reinforcement of window cutout; right – frame)

4.3 INFUSION TECHNOLOGIES

All advanced infusion technologies have been taken into account, such as

- RTM
- RI
- Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI)

Especially VARI (see figure 5) shows big potential for cost reduction during manufacturing. Key detail for a successful application is the use of semi-permeable membranes, which have been developed to industrial standard within the project.

VARI and related technologies are introduced into AIRBUS composite manufacturing.

Figure 5 – VARI Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion

4.4 THERMOPLASTIC MATERIALS AND -PROCESSES

Massive work has been put into the creation of new thermoplastic matrix systems, which combine the advantages of a significantly lower material price compared to APC2a/AS4 (PEEK) and high mechanical performance.

New ternary blends (e.g. PEEK / PEI / PSU) have been developed with good prospects as far as material costs are concerned.

In comparison with thermoset systems, thermoplastics still cannot prove to be competitive. For a realization of verification parts and test panels, thermoplastics will only play a minor role for double skin fuselage applications.

4.5 BONDING MATERIALS AND –TECHNOLOGIES

Still riveting remains the standard assembly technology for aircraft structures. After successful introduction of co-curing and co-bonding of overall composite structures, like AIRBUS empennage or high-lift components, the new bonding technology paste bonding (see figure 6) is in the moment being introduced in AIRBUS manufacturing lines.

Paste bonding should be used to the utmost extent for the realization of typical fuselage test articles. Main benefits of this technology are:

- Low temperature curing
- No need for autoclaving
- Tolerance bandwidth of adhesive layer allows automated application

In order to reinforce locally against impact, z-fibers are a very promising candidate to enhance mechanical performance.

Carbon or glass z-fibers can be applied by using ultrasonic means to reinforce e.g. joints from fames to skin or comparable composite fuselage structures (see figure 6).

Figure 6 – Stress Analysis of a Paste Bonding Joint (left) – Z-Fiber Reinforcement (right)

4.6 CORE MATERIALS

To realize double skin structures, the development of advanced core materials is mandatory. Standard honeycombs are not suitable due to damage tolerance and moisture absorption problems. For an application as structural core material, advanced folded structures (see figure 7) are favored. In cooperation with international partners such structures are being optimized in terms of material selection, geometry and mechanical performance.

Figure 7 - Folded Structures

In first analytical surveys, folded structures promise to deliver supreme impact tolerance performance, in combination with a possibility for ventilation (moisture management) and acoustical insulation features.

5. MANUFACTURING APPROACHES

Basically, an optimum composite design is considered to contribute significantly to mission success. In a first theoretical approach, an advanced design sees larger sections, less frames and less cutouts, compared to the metal baseline. Such a change in manufacturing philosophy may result in a possible weight reduction of 15% (see figure 8).

Optimum Composite design (larger sections, less frames, less cutouts) as basis for success.

Figure 8 - Global Manufacturing Approach; Comparison Metal Baseline to Dedicated Composite Design

For typical sections of the fuselage, different manufacturing technologies are evaluated in cooperation with research institutes and international industrial partners. Double skin design is the technological basis for typical fuselage.

Manufacturing scenarios for typical fuselage see the use of advanced core materials in combination with stiffened panels. Those stiffened panels will have to be manufactured weight and cost effective, e.g. by combining prepreg- and infusion technology at minimized tooling expenditure.

Overall, the complete chain of aircraft manufacturing is taken under consideration. Various approaches and technologies are being followed in the fields of

New materials & Processes => Manufacturing => Assembly => Testing => In-Service

On the field of testing technology, two ways of development are followed. For quality control related to the manufacturing process, laser-ultrasonic measuring could be a future means to significantly reduce cycle times. Laser-shearography may be used in service or field repair (see figure 9).

One showcase technology for surface treatment, which can have very positive effects on maintenance efforts, is an integrated system for moisture management (see figure 9), which has two basic functions

- Regulation of moisture resulting from dewing mechanisms around the double skin structure
- Enhancement of passenger comfort in the cabin

Figure 9 – Example for Component Testing by Shearography (left) – Moisture Management (right)

6. PROCEEDING

AIRBUS composite fuselage work is concentrated and coordinated by a transnational cluster organization. This organization guarantees that all efforts of the national sites, which are traditionally targeting at the work share of national facilities, are combined under the one roof of AIRBUS.

In addition to that, projects on European level will handle all the topics that cannot be dealt with on national basis.

7. CONCLUSION

New materials, processes and manufacturing technologies will contribute to reach the project goals 30/40/++. This goal can only be achieved in a common effort of AIRBUS engineers, research institutions and material providers in a long-term developmental project. A CFRP fuselage for the next generation AIRBUS aircraft features an innovative design, driven by mechanical optimization and advanced materials and processes.